

Protective effect of black rice extract on the functional status of liver and hepatic stellate cell against toxicity induced by ethanol

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Abstract : The present study was performed to investigate the protective effect of black rice ethanolic extract (BREE) on liver injury induced by ethyl alcohol in male rats. The study was conducted on 40 male Wistar rats weighing (190–200 g), the animals were divided into 4 equal groups. The first group was received basal diet and used as a normal control group (NC). The second group were administered ethyl alcohol (6 g/kg bw) orally and used as positive control (PC). The other groups of rats were administered ethyl alcohol (6 mg/kg bw) + BREE (125 and 250 mg/kg bw/day). Blood and tissue samples were collected after 2 weeks. The results revealed that the rats treated with ethyl alcohol showed a significant ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in levels of TC, TL, TG, ALT and AST. Ethyl alcohol intoxication induces some pathological alterations in the liver as degeneration of cytoplasm and nuclei manifest clear symptoms of pyknosis and karyorrhexis. The rise in serum hepatic enzymes, TC, TL, TG, histopathological and immunohistochemical changes were significantly attenuated by BREE. The current results clearly investigate the beneficial effects of BREE in controlling ethyl alcohol disorders induced and the protection of liver against ethyl alcohol intoxication.

Keywords : Antioxidants, black rice extract, ethanol, immunohistochemical, free radicals, rats.

Introduction

Liver has an important role in the metabolism and detoxification of the majority substances entering human body. Toxic chemicals, excessive consumption of alcohol and virus infections can cause liver injuries to different extent^{1,2}. The susceptibility of liver to ethanol toxicity can promote alcoholic liver disease³.

Alcohol has been suspected to be a major cause of liver disease for centuries and its ingestion causes liver damage⁴. Progression to an alcoholic liver disease is a multifactorial process that involves a number of genetic, nutritional and environmental factors⁵. Ethanol affects almost all organs of the body because of its ability to permeate all tissues due to its water and fat soluble properties. Among various mechanisms implicated in the pathogenesis of alcoholic liver disease, the ability of acute and chronic ethanol treatment to increase production of reactive oxygen species (ROS) and enhance peroxidation of lipids, protein carbonyl formation, formation of the 1-hydroxyethyl radical, formation of lipid radicals, and de-

creases in hepatic antioxidant defense, especially GSH⁶⁻¹⁰, and DNA has been demonstrated in a variety of systems, cells, and species, including humans. Several studies indicated that ethanol metabolism via alcohol dehydrogenase results in an increase in ROS production, hepatocyte injury, and apoptosis, reactions blocked by antioxidants in control rats or chronically ethanol-fed rats^{11,12}. Histopathological features of alcoholic liver disease include fat accumulation and hepatitis, followed by fibrosis and cirrhosis also were noted. In the rat liver, when ethanol-containing diet is delivered continuously, pathological changes reflective of human alcoholic liver disease occur (i.e. fat accumulation, inflammation, and fibrosis). One hypothesis to account for the mechanism of alcohol induced liver injury is that CYP2E1, induced predominantly in hepatocytes by ethanol, increases production of free radicals. Also, Kupffer cells, the resident hepatic macrophages, play a key role in alcohol induced liver damage^{13,14}. Moreover, ethanol causes formation of α -hydroxyethyl radical in rats. On the other hand, alcohol

increases gut permeability for Gram-negative bacterial endotoxin. Endotoxin is a potent activator of Kupffer cells, which release toxic cytokines and inflammatory mediators (e.g. TNF- α) as well as reactive oxygen species. Indeed, Kupffer cells may be the source of oxidants¹⁵.

Hepatic fibrosis is a common outcome of liver injury. Activated fibroblasts which develop myofibroblastic characteristics play an essential role in hepatic fibrogenesis. Fibrocontractive diseases are characterized by the presence of a cell called myofibroblast that is responsible for pathological tissue remodeling. Perisinusoidally located hepatic stellate cells are considered the major source of myofibroblasts in the injured liver¹⁶. Hepatic stellate cells (HSCs) in the normal liver are quiescent, long-lived cells situated in the space of Disse and bearing cytoplasmic processes that embrace the sinusoids, thereby facilitating their interaction with neighboring cell types¹⁷. HSCs are the predominant source of extracellular matrix collagen in the liver, and their activation is the earliest step in hepatic fibrogenesis, collagen deposition, and progressive fibrosis leading to cirrhosis. Following liver injury, HSCs undergo activation and *trans* differentiation to myofibroblast like cells¹⁸.

Research on natural plant ingredients with potential hepatoprotective activity for functional food and nutraceutical development has been a hot topic in many fields, including nutrition and natural product chemistry. Black rice (*Oryza sativa* L.) is a good source of fiber, minerals, and phytochemicals besides basic nutrients (Fig. 1)^{19,20}. It has a wide range of beneficial properties including hepatoprotective²¹, anticancer, antioxidant^{22,23}, and anti-inflammatory properties²⁴. Additionally, black rice has a distinct compositions of phytochemicals, especially phenolics, flavonoids and anthocyanins, which have

Fig. 1. Black rice grains.

been shown to have beneficial effects in the prevention of chronic diseases²⁵. Organic solvents absolute methanol, ethanol and acetone are commonly used for the extract phenolic antioxidants from plant materials to obtain the phenolic fraction due to its simplicity and low cost^{26–28}. Several studies have reported the hepatoprotective effect of anthocyanin extracts from natural food and plants²⁹. Moreover, it has antioxidant, free radical scavenging activities³⁰, improved lipid profiles³¹, prevent or treat hypercholesterolaemia^{32,33} and may reduce the risks of oxidative stress, cancer with anti-inflammatory and chemoprotective properties³⁴.

As for black rice, there is, to the best of our knowledge, only two studies involved in the hepatoprotective effect on alcohol in toxicated rats^{35,36}. Previous studies on black rice mainly focused on anthocyanins, not the antioxidant extract and the immunohistochemistry characteristics. Therefore, the main objective of this study was to investigate the prevention of black rice ethanolic extract against ethanol-induced hepatotoxicity in rats, and to investigate the immunohistochemical characteristics of hepatic myofibroblasts and hepatic stellate cells in liver diseases.

Materials and methods :

Preparation of black rice ethanolic extract :

Black rice was ground by blender (Waring 2-Liter Laboratory Blender – The Lab Depot Inc). Then, a weighed portion (100 g) of black rice was extracted with 150 ml of ethyl alcohol for 24 h. The ethanolic extract of ethyl was filtered through Whatman No. 4 filter paper. Solvent extraction was repeated twice and the extract solution was combined and kept at 4 °C until used.

Biological methods :

Male albino adult rats (40 animals weighing 190–200 g) were obtained from Vaccination Center, Helwan, Giza, Egypt, then transported to Animal House of Ophthalmology Research Institute, Giza, Egypt. Rats were housed in individual cages with screen bottoms and fed on basal diet (corn starch 70%, casein 10%, corn seed oil 10%, cellulose 5%, salt mixture 4% and vitamins mixture 1%) for ten days. After equilibration, rats were weighted and divided into four groups (ten animals per each) everyone was assigned to one of the four diet groups, [negative control (NC)], positive control (PC) treated with ethyl

alcohol orally (6 g/kg bw/day) and two groups treated with ethyl alcohol (6 g/kg bw/day) + black rice ethanolic extract (125 and 250 mg/kg bw/day) orally. Total feed consumption was weighted, fresh feed was provided every day and total body weight of the animals was recorded at the beginning and during the experimental period. At the end of the experiment, the animals of each group were killed by decapitation. Blood samples were collected from the orbital plexus by mean of heparinized capillary glass tubes according to Schermer³⁷. Each sample was placed into a dry clean centrifuge tube and centrifuged 1500 xg for 30 min at 4 °C to obtain serum.

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Biochemical assays :

sAST and sALT assay :

Serum transaminases sAST and sALT (Aspartate transferase and Alanine transferase) were measured calorimetrically according to the method described by Reitman and Frankel³⁸.

TC, TL and TG assays :

Total cholesterol (TC) was determined according to the method described by Allain *et al.*³⁹, total lipids (TL) were determined according to the method described by Kinght *et al.*⁴⁰ and triglycerides (TG) were determined according to the method described by Fossati and Prencipe⁴¹.

Light microscopic processing :

Hepatic histology :

At the end treatment liver fragments were fixed in buffered formalin for 2–4 h and embedded in paraffin with a melting point of 55–57 °C. Three to four-micrometer sections were cut and stained with hematoxylin-eosin and Masson's trichrome stains.

Immunohistochemistry :

For immunohistochemical studies, the sections were mounted on glass slides coated with 0.1% poly (L-lysine). After deparaffination and subsequent blockage of the endogenous peroxidase activity by incubation in 2.5% methanolic hydrogen peroxide (30 min), the endogenous biotin was blocked by the Biotin Blocking System (Dako, Milan, Italy) according to the instructions received from the vendor. The sections were then washed 3 times in phosphate-buffered saline, the sections were processed as

described elsewhere. Mouse monoclonal anti-SMA antibody (Dako 1A4) diluted 1 : 40. The sections were incubated for 1 h at room temperature with anti-SMA at 4 °C. After 3 washings in phosphate-buffered saline, the sections were incubated for 30 min with the appropriate secondary biotinylated antibody labeled with the avidin-biotin complex (labeled streptavidin-biotin; Dako code K0675). Negative controls were performed with normal mouse antiserum instead of the primary antibody, which uniformly demonstrated no reaction. The sections were developed with 3,3-diaminobenzidine and finally counterstained with hematoxylin and cleared in xylene and mounted in Canada blasma (Kiernan⁶⁰). The section were then examined under light microscope.

Statistical analysis :

Results were expressed as mean SEM. The intergroup variation was measured by one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) followed by Fischer's LSD test. Statistical significance was considered at ($p \leq 0.05$). The statistical analysis was done using the Jandel Sigma Stat Statistical Software version 2.0.

Results and discussion

The liver weight was found to be increased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) in animals fed with ethanol as compared to NC, while it decreased significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) in the BREE G4 group (250 mg/kg bw) compared to PC, suggesting that supplementation of BREE with the ethanol reduced liver weight, which is similar to the previous reports³⁶. It has been indicated that hepatic steatosis has been defined as either more than 5% of hepatocytes containing fat droplets or total lipid exceeding 5% of liver weight⁶.

Effect of BREE on AST and ALT activities :

In our study, we observed a significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) increase in the activities of liver marker enzymes such as AST and ALT on ethanol intoxicated rats (Table 2), which indicates increased permeability, damage and/or necrosis of hepatocytes and cause severe damage to tissue membrane⁴². Ethanol ingestion causes liver damage with the leakage of cellular enzymes into plasma being a sign of hepatic injury⁴³. During liver injury, transport function of the hepatocytes is disturbed which leads to leakage of plasma membrane, thereby causing an increased enzyme level in serum⁴⁴. Also, alcohol-induced oxidative stress

Table 1. Effect of BREE on liver weight in ethanol-administrated rats

Treatments	Liver weight (g/g bw)
G1 (NC)	0.03564 ^c ± 0.00007
G2 (PC)	0.04404 ^a ± 0.00052
G3 (125 mg/kg bw BREE)	0.03866 ^b ± 0.00008
G4 (250 mg/kg bw BREE)	0.03596 ^c ± 0.00006
LSD	7.95E – 04

Table 2. Effect of BREE on ALT and AST activities in ethanol-administrated rats

Treatments	ALT (U/L)	AST (U/L)
G1 (NC)	37.34 ^d ± 0.07	25.09 ^d ± 0.03
G2 (PC)	66.99 ^a ± 0.04	44.73 ^a ± 0.18
G3 (125 mg/kg bw BREE)	43.23 ^b ± 0.06	29.10 ^b ± 0.06
G4 (250 mg/kg bw BREE)	38.17 ^c ± 0.06	25.88 ^c ± 0.08
LSD	0.175	0.306

Table 3. Effect of BREE on TC, TG and TL in ethanol-administrated rats

Treatments	TC (mg/dl)	TG (mg/dl)	TL (mg/dl)
G1 (NC)	148.85 ^d ± 0.09	124.69 ^d ± 0.12	516.73 ^c ± 0.08
G2 (PC)	288.39 ^a ± 0.41	224.88 ^a ± 0.12	817.75 ^a ± 0.24
G3 (125 mg/kg bw BREE)	198.80 ^b ± 0.07	164.41 ^b ± 0.14	615.89 ^b ± 0.24
G4 (250 mg/kg bw BREE)	150.16 ^c ± 0.13	131.74 ^c ± 0.12	516.23 ^c ± 0.20
LSD	0.670	0.378	0.603

BREE = Black rice ethanolic extract.

Statistically significant at $p \leq 0.05$ as compared to NC (one way ANOVA followed by Fischer's LSD test).

in the liver cells plays a major role in the development of alcoholic liver disease. Oxidative stress-mediated interference with mitochondrial functions, protein degradation, insulin signaling and lipoprotein secretion likely contribute to the development of alcoholic steatosis^{45–47}.

In the present study rats administration of BREE significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) decreased the activities of AST and ALT, which indicate the hepatoprotective effect. Treatment with BREE (250 mg/kg bw) significantly alleviates the decreased activities of liver marker enzymes to near normal levels (Table 2), which may be a consequence of stabilization of serum membrane and maintaining the functional status of the liver from ethanol toxicity. Reports also show that BRE exerted liver benefits mainly by its antioxidant activity^{35,48}. Regular consumption of black

rice might be beneficial for the alleviation of oxidative stress in human body and for people's liver health^{36,49,50}.

Effect of BREE on TC, TG and TL levels :

Levels of TC, TG and TL in serum are presented in Table 3. We found that, in rats being fed ethanol (PC), led to the increase of serum TC, TG and TL levels ($p \leq 0.05$). BREE G3 group (125 mg/kg bw) supplementation improved these adverse effects. Serum levels of TC, TG and TL (198.80 mg/dl, 64.41 mg/dl, 615.89 mg/dl), respectively, significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) decreased compared with the PC (288.39 mg/dl, 224.88 mg/dl, 817.75 mg/dl), respectively. On the other hand, BREE G4 group (250 mg/kg bw) administrated rats gave the best results compared to NC (Table 3). Accumulation of fat is the earliest and most common response to heavy alcohol intake. Alcoholic fatty liver is usually characterized by the enlargement of the liver, the increase of the serum TG levels, together with a lot of fat droplets in the liver sections^{7,51}. In this study, ethanol administration resulted in the considerable increase of liver index, the elevation of the serum TC, TG and TL levels (Table 3), suggesting that ethanol administration induced typical fatty liver. Parallel to these changes, histological examination showed a lot of droplets in ethanol-treated rat livers, and this agree with previous study³⁵. In the present study, we found that, supplementation of BREE G4 group (250 mg/kg bw) significantly ($p \leq 0.05$) reduced serum levels of TC, TG and TL levels compared with the PC. We show that the antioxidant extract from black rice has the property of preventing from ethanol-induced hepatotoxicity in rats by improving lipid profile. These results are similar with previous study which suggest that black rice containing cyanidin-3-glucoside is a healthful food that may be useful in the reducing the risks of hepatic steatosis⁵² and its related disorders such as hyperlipidemia and hyperglycemia^{35,53–55}.

Histopathological examination of rat's liver :

Histology examination with H and E of rat's liver :

Photomicrograph Fig. 2 A1 of a liver section of control rats showed strands of hepatocytes which embodied darkly eosinophilic cytoplasm, highly sinusoids (HS) and binucleated cell (BC). Also, Fig. 2 A2 showed the portal area containing the hepatic portal vein (*), Kupffer cell (CK), hepatic artery (A) and bile ductule (BD). The liver

samples of alcohol-treated rats in Fig. 1 B1 showed the central vein (CV) conspicuous dilation and engorged with stagnant haemolysed blood. Moreover, vacuolar degradation of cytoplasm of hepatocytes (thin arrow), nuclei (thick arrow) manifest clear symptoms of pyknosis and karyorrhexis. The central vein appeared markedly dilated, deposition of materials amoeboid and surrounded with inflammatory cells (IC) (Fig. 2 B2).

Fig. 2. Light micrograph of liver section of normal control rat's NC (A1 and A2), positive control (PC) (B1 and B2), ethyl alcohol + BREE (125 mg/kg bw) (C1 and C2) and ethyl alcohol + BREE (250 mg/kg bw) (D1 and D2), H and E x400.

It was found that administration of BREE reversed this liver damage. BREE at a dose of (250 mg/kg bw) (Fig. 2 D1, D2) was more effective when compared with the other dose (125 mg/kg bw) (Fig. 2 C1, C2). The administration of ethanol along with BREE (125 mg/kg bw) showed irregular liver stripes around the central vein (arrow) despite the presence of a simple congestion pellets red blood (Fig. 2 C1), decomposition of the cytoplasmic

mic liver cells, and the emergence of many branches of the bile ductule (head arrow) (Fig. 2 C2) are also noted. The administration of ethanol along with BREE (250 mg/kg bw) showed near normal appearance. Most hepatocytes appearance naturally (thin arrow), dark cell cytoplasm and nuclei of normal (thick arrow), except for the decomposition of simple and infiltration of inflammatory cells (Fig. 2 D1, D2).

Our results showed that ethanol can induce severe liver damage. Histopathological signs of alcoholic liver injury : steatosis, inflammation and necrosis. The liver restored histoarchitecture similar to NC, and this agree with other research which suggested that the focal hepatocytic necrosis with inflammatory cell infiltration in alcohol-treated rats might be due to the accumulation of lipids and its content in tissues, which could also increase the lipid peroxidation (LPO), as a basis for cellular damage³⁵. Administration of BREE remarkably reduced the histological alterations caused by alcohol, which may be due to attenuation of the ethanol-mediated oxidative threat and reduction of the pathological changes with restoration of normal physiological function³⁶.

Histochemistry examination (Collagen fiber) by using masson trichrom stain rat's liver :

In normal liver tissue, the perisinusoidal liver cells play role in pathogenesis fiber contractive change, using light microscopic (Masson trichrom) and immunolocalization technique, in this study, the liver section of normal control (NC) group showed the thin layer from collagen fiber (blue in masson trichrom stain) around central vein (CV) and supported for walls of sinusoidal (arrow) (Fig. 3 A1) and portal veins (head arrow) (Fig. 3 A2). While, liver section of ethanolic (6 mg/kg bw) group showed the collagen fiber accumulation were detected preferentially in periportal or perivenular zones according to the location of underlying hepatocellular damage (arrow) (Fig. 3 B1, B2).

The liver section from the group administration of BREE at a dose of (125 mg/kg bw) (Fig. 3 C1, C2) was found the collagen fiber accumulation the same location but less than group treated with alcoholic (arrow).

In contrast, the administration of ethanol along with BREE (250 mg/kg bw) (Fig. 3 D1, D2) showed improved appears as a low density collagen fiber (arrow) compared to the ethanolic group (Fig. 3 B1, B2).

Fig. 3. Light micrograph of liver section of normal control rat's NC (A1 and A2), positive control (PC) (B1 and B2), ethyl alcohol + BREE (125 mg/kg bw) (C1 and C2) and ethyl alcohol + BREE (250 mg/kg bw) (D1 and D2), masson trichrom x400.

Immunohistochemical study of rat's liver :

Alcoholic can induce severe liver damage. The liver samples of ethanolic-treated rats showed some immunohistochemical changes in the liver. Liver section of normal control (NC) group showing the dye positive for alpha-actin filaments in most cells (arrow), particularly the cells surrounding the hepatic vein blood grained (Fig. 4 A1, A2). While, liver section of ethanolic (6 mg/kg bw) group showing the intensity of the dye positive for alpha-actin filaments as shown in centrilobular regions (arrow) (Fig. 4 B1) and in portal space (head arrow) (Fig. 4 B2), but in more severe cases may involve the entire lobule. Lipid vacuoles occupy much of the hepatocyte cytoplasm, pushing the nucleus and other organelles to the periphery of the cell and histological evidence of HSC hypertrophy (increase in the number of lipid droplets per cell) and

hyperplasia (increase in the number of HSCs). It was found that administration of BREE (125 mg/kg bw) exhibited higher protective effects (arrow) (Fig. 4 C1, C2) when compared to ethanolic administrated rats (Fig. 4 B1, B2). On the other hand, BREE (250 mg/kg bw) administrated rats showed immunological pattern to near normalcy (arrow) (Fig. 4 D1, D2). It gave weakness in the intensity of the dye positive for alpha-actin filaments.

Fig. 4. Light micrograph of liver section of normal control rat's NC (A1 and A2), positive control (PC) (B1 and B2), ethyl alcohol + BREE (125 mg/kg bw) (C1 and C2) and ethyl alcohol + BREE (250 mg/kg bw) (D1 and D2), immunohistochemical stain (anti-SMA) x400.

In various types of chronic liver disease, it has been shown that HSCs play an important role in fibrogenesis⁵⁶. HSC activation might represent the net result of retinol toxicity, release of pro-inflammatory cytokines as well as fibrogenic products by damaged hepatocytes. As far as liver fibrosis is concerned, our data indicate that in addition to a strong correlation between HSCs activation and

the total amount of fibrotic tissue present in the biopsy. Lefkowitz (2005) study the early stage of liver injury in the alcoholic and reported that the damage to the liver cells may be shown microscopically by the accumulation of fat, by hydropic swelling and by hyaline change⁵⁷. All these are probably reversible, although severe hyaline change does proceed to necrosis. The presence of increased connective tissue around the central veins and along the sinusoidal walls in the absence of any other significant lesion was unexpected. Although it cannot be definitely stated that this excess connective tissue forms without any comitant liver cell injury, we were unable, in some biopsy specimens, to observe any such injury with the light microscope. We know that more advanced fibrosis is often associated with hyaline necrosis of parenchymal cells. The exact relationship of the two type's injury is not clear. Some of the material in the walls of the sinusoids that stains with Masson's trichrome stain may be material other than collagen; but, on electron microscopic studies, collagen fibers were easily demonstrated in our material.

Our results clearly showed that antioxidant in BREE displayed significant beneficial protective effects on ethanol-induced liver injury. This protective effect is mainly due to its free radical scavenging activity which has been suggested as a possible mechanism of action of BREE against cellular toxicity. Furthermore, the high content of polyphenols, steroids and saponins present in BREE efficiently retards the liver injury by blocking oxidative stress and enhancing antioxidant status and thus preventing from organ damage and necrosis and these results agree with the previous studies^{58,59}. Therefore, dietary supplementation of BREE offers protection against liver toxicity. Further studies are warranted to elucidate the mechanisms of action and identifying the active compounds from BREE against cellular and organ toxicity.

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